

Assessing the Modern Employee Management Strategies for Optimum Organizational Productivity in Nigeria

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Abstract

This research paper is an empirical study to assess the modern employee management strategies for optimum organizational productivity in Nigeria. The study also seeks to ascertain the degree of connection between modern employee management strategies and organizational productivity. The study employed a descriptive survey design approach with One-Sample Test statistics. Information was gathered from 133 employees of fast food restaurants in Asaba, Delta State, using a standardized questionnaire with a Likert scale. The study's conclusions show that modern staff management techniques and organizational productivity are significantly positively correlated. This is crucial since it increases the organization's overall productivity, survivability, and sustainability. As a result, companies should make sure that their HR practices are human-centered. The study also demonstrated a strong and favorable relationship between the effectiveness of hiring and selecting procedures and the survival of contemporary enterprises. This implies that human resource management's recruitment and selection processes can help employees cultivate a good work attitude and enhance the performance and survival of modern firms by attracting and choosing the best applicants. The empirical study found a substantial correlation between organizational success, training and development, and the survival of contemporary businesses. The study concludes that a human-centric HRM approach and modern employee management strategies are necessary in the modern workplace to guarantee full employee engagement and the best talent retention in modern business as well as optimum organizational productivity. The study therefore recommends that modern organizations combine the above-mentioned comprehensive and human-centric HRM practices and employee management strategies with AI workplace automation, which shortens turnaround times and increases organizational productivity and effectiveness. The introduction of AI should be human-centered and not aimed at replacing human labour.

Keywords: Modern Employee Management Strategies, Organizational Productivity, Human Resource Management, Recruitment and Selection, Employee retention

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1. Introduction

Managing employees entails helping them succeed in their positions and coordinating their efforts with the goals and mission of the company. This procedure covers every stage of the job lifecycle, from hiring to firing. Effective employee management focuses on building good relationships throughout an employee's journey, even while there isn't a one-size-fits-all strategy. It also entails monitoring and assessing their performance in relation to predetermined professional goals. The ability of managers to motivate, communicate, and establish trust with their teams is a key component of effective staff management. The best managers act as coaches, praising present accomplishments and promoting ongoing development (Chukwuka & Dibie 2024).

Human resource management, or HRM, is a planned, coordinated, and integrated approach to the employment, development, and welfare of people within a company. Human resource management encompasses all administrative decisions and actions that affect the nature of the relationship between the organization and its human resources, or its personnel (Chukwuka & Nwakoby 2018). HRM is a distinctive approach to employment management that employs a range of integrated people, structural, and cultural methods to strategically deploy a highly competent and dedicated workforce in order to obtain a competitive advantage (Carnevale & Hatak 2020).

An increasing number of performance evaluations consider other aspects of organizational life. According to Chukwuka and Dibie (2024), companies aim to attract top personnel and fulfill customer desires. As a result, companies are becoming more aware of how other elements contribute to their success. Companies also consider the well-being and health of their workforce. The well-being of employees directly affects their productivity and ability to achieve objectives. Stakeholder connections, sustainability, and social responsibility are further factors that organizations consider.

Knowing what is expected of them improves employee performance. The goals are communicated to the staff by the HR management. According to Amrutha and Geetha (2020), HR is also responsible for performance reviews. As a result, the HR division assesses goals and performance levels. The company's performance seems to be dependent on how its human resources department operates. It is crucial to look at how HR managers perceive their contribution to the company's performance. Assessing how employees view HR managers' involvement in organizational management is equally important. Other HR practices, like as hiring, firing, benefits, and wellness, may have an impact on the company's success. Hiring new employees, for example, is the responsibility of HR.

1.2 Statement of Problem and the Justification for this Study

Despite the availability of contemporary employee management techniques including performance management systems, flexible work schedules, digital HR tools, and employee engagement programs, many Nigerian businesses still suffer with poor or subpar employee productivity. The entire potential of the workforce is frequently unrealized by traditional, bureaucratic systems to employee management, which are typified by top-down decision-making, insufficient feedback channels, and little investment in training and well-being. This has

undermined organizational competitiveness and the growth of the national economy by causing high turnover, low morale, and poor performance in both public and private sector organizations.

Additionally, there is a dearth of empirical data regarding the adoption and adaptation of modern employee management strategies (such as remote/hybrid work, continuous feedback, performance-based incentives, and technology-enabled HR processes) in the Nigerian context, as well as how these practices actually affect productivity levels. Because of this, managers and policymakers frequently rely on global models without fully comprehending their contextual fit or quantifiable impact in Nigeria's distinct socioeconomic and cultural setting.

The urgent need to close the gap between contemporary human resource management theory and practical application in Nigeria justifies this study. Organizations must maximize the productivity of their current personnel rather than depending exclusively on staff or capital expansion due to recurrent economic downturns, skill shortages, and growing operating costs. Evaluating contemporary employee management techniques offers useful information about whether procedures (including goal-setting frameworks, performance feedback systems, flexible work schedules, and digital tools) actually increase productivity in Nigerian companies.

The findings will also assist organizations in shifting from ad hoc or antiquated personnel practices to evidence-based HR policies that are adapted to regional circumstances including labor laws, cultural norms, and infrastructure limitations. The study will help policymakers create labor and industrial relations frameworks that promote contemporary, compassionate, and effective workplaces. Academically, it will add to the expanding corpus of literature on productivity and human resource management in Nigeria and act as a resource for upcoming scholars and students studying public administration, management, and business.

The main objective of this study is to assess the Modern Employee Management Strategies for Optimum Productivity in Nigeria and to confirm the degree of connection between modern Employee management strategies and Employment productivity.

Literature Review

2.1 The concept of Employee Management Strategy

The term "employee management strategies for optimal productivity" refers to the methodical ways managers organize, plan, inspire, and oversee staff members in order to maximize individual and team outputs while maintaining engagement and morale. These tactics combine human-relations abilities with organized methods for development, performance, and communication (Chukwuka & Igweh 2025). Employee management style or strategy also refers to the approach, methods, and techniques that managers use to direct, motivate, supervise, and develop employees within an organization to achieve organizational goals effectively (Chukwuka & Nwakoby 2018).

Key elements of employee Management strategy include: Leadership Approach which depicts way a manager provides direction and makes decisions (e.g., authoritative or participative). Communication Pattern, which shows how information flows between managers and employees, open, formal, or restricted. Decision-Making Process, which explains whether

decisions are made solely by management or involve employee input. Motivation Techniques, this is used to inspire employees, such as rewards, recognition, or incentives. Control and Supervision, this entails the degree of monitoring and oversight applied to employees' work.

Different management Style has distinct effects on an organization's productivity. The capacity of HR managers to accomplish their goals is influenced by HR management strategies or styles. When management uses total quality management as the main method of putting organizational strategies into practice, better performance is the result (Aziz et al., 2019). HR managers might choose from a variety of management philosophies. The research results on how various HR management philosophies affect organizational success are reviewed in this section.

Employee-friendly leadership approaches are favoured above those that restrict their independence. The transformative leadership style is the most effective. This leadership style encourages learning and creativity within the company, claim Para-González et al. (2018). By encouraging the efficient use of technology use and knowledge management techniques, transformational leadership accomplishes this goal (Sayyadi, 2019). As a result, HR managers that use the approach encourage improved performance within their companies.

Leadership styles also affect performance by fostering the ideal organizational culture, as the literature now in publication explains. Strong leaders encourage a common set of values inside the company, which raises the likelihood of achieving the goals (Tan, 2019). Thus, in HR management, influential leadership styles are favoured. These leaders inspire their staff to stay productive and achieve their goals (Al Khajeh, 2018). Therefore, when staff productivity rises, so do performance levels.

The transactional leadership style is another favoured leadership approach. Knowledge management is superior in organizations where HR management employs a transactional leadership style. Organizations' perform better when HR managers employ knowledge management to foster innovation, according to a study done among SMEs (Singh et al., 2021). According to the literature currently under publication, knowledge management is essential for raising organizational performance levels.

Poor organizational performance is linked to specific management philosophies. Employees are less likely to be creative and highly productive when their freedom is restricted by their leaders. Charismatic and transactional leadership styles are examples of leadership style that deprive workers of their independence and opportunity (Al Khajeh, 2018).

Academics advise against HR managers using either of the two leadership style. Desired leadership styles generally encourage employees' ability to achieve well. Organizational success is favourably correlated with HR strategies that foster opportunity, ability, and motivation (Anwar et al., 2020). Therefore, it is vital to examine how staff members view their managers. The study will try to find out if workers believe they have the freedom to be creative and act quickly. Additionally, the study will examine which management philosophies employees find most effective and which they dislike.

Employees Are Affected by Human Resource Management HR procedures have an impact on workers' happiness and well-being, which in turn affects their ability to function properly (Peccei & Van De Voorde, 2019). When HR procedures are properly carried out, employees are generally satisfied with the company and their jobs. Employees that have distinct job roles are less likely to experience burnout and weariness, which leads to happiness (Marescaux et al., 2018). Consequently, HR management has an impact on employees' working environments.

Employee performance and productivity are influenced by their well-being. High levels of conflict, violence, low productivity, and poor performance at work are all correlated with low employee well-being (Zhou et al., 2020). As they try to manage their employees' performance, many organizations are now interested in keeping an eye on their well-being (Skurak et al., 2018). By taking care of their employees' well-being, organizations strive to improve performance. A toxic workplace that impairs employee engagement, productivity, and well-being can be avoided by HR managers by fostering a positive culture (Rasool et al., 2021). Additionally, HR professionals can impact employee well-being by providing employees with the tools and learning opportunities they need to develop in their careers (Huo & Boxall, 2020). Workers who have access to these resources perform better because they are more content. Managers' interactions with staff members have an impact on their wellbeing, which in turn affects how well they perform.

Achieving work-life balance is also emphasized in the literature as a means of improving performance. Work commitment and performance levels are influenced by an individual's perception of work-life balance (Wong et al., 2021). Work-life balance and employee engagement are difficult for employers to manage (Wood et al., 2020). Employers who place too much emphasis on job engagement risk having workers who don't have a good work-life balance. These workers perform poorly. Organizations' that place a high priority on work-life balance risk not meeting their performance goals.

By assisting companies in striking a balance between employee work-life balance and work engagement, HR management affects performance. Through human resource development, HR management distributes resources for workers to utilise, which in turn affects how long each task takes (Wood et al., 2020). Thus, HR professionals have a direct impact on workplace productivity. Employees can work effectively within the allotted time and take their time off when all resources are available. Technology can also be used by management to make sure that workers have access to tools that encourage effective performance (Prasanna et al., 2019). Therefore, by increasing their level of engagement at work, HR management can have an impact on employee performance.

The nature of the relationships that exist between employers and employees is another approach to affect performance. Because employees promote the company, companies with positive management-employee connections have a great brand (Korzynski et al., 2020). Because their staff serves as brand ambassadors, these companies have a high level of brand recognition and reputation. Brand ambassadors encourage marketing innovation for their organisations, which in turn encourages market supremacy (Hussain et al., 2020). Therefore, HR managers should try to build stronger relationships with their staff in order to turn them into brand ambassadors.

Because it improves an organization's financial performance, brand awareness is desired. Because they gain the trust of their customers, companies with a good reputation and brand awareness perform better in the marketplace (Foroudi, 2019). As a result, they improve sales and draw in additional clients. Analysing sales based on client acquisition and retention strategies is one method of assessing a company's performance (Narayanaswamy & Heiens, 2022). Strong brands make it easy for businesses to draw in and keep consumers. As a result, they do better in the market. According to the review, the detrimental effects of management on staff are not given enough consideration. In order to close this gap, the study will examine how workers perceive management's detrimental influence.

2.2. The impact of modern technology to employee management

Technology has an impact on HR management, which in turn affects organizational performance. HR management now has more options to improve organizational performance thanks to technological improvements. Anwar and Abdullah (2020) assert that by controlling staff and customer happiness, businesses may leverage technology to improve performance. There are numerous tools available for HR managers to use in their work.

Technology has altered how HR procedures are implemented. The ability of HR managers to carry out their diverse responsibilities has improved due to technological advancements (Fenech et al., 2019). To make effective judgments during HR practice, for instance, HR management can now rely on technology (Vrontis et al., 2021). HR management has a bigger effect on performance using these tools. Since HR managers can communicate in real time with all employees, even virtual teams, the impact can be more immediate and direct.

A variety of methods are available to HR managers to improve practice performance. For instance, HR managers can expedite and improve the efficiency of the hiring process by using technology to screen applications (Vrontis et al., 2021). HR managers can therefore fill positions more quickly. Additionally, managers can train staff members and make sure they are capable of performing as needed by using technology (Vrontis et al., 2021). Finally, HR managers can use technology to convey performance goals, track performance levels, and make adjustments to guarantee that goals are met (Vrontis et al., 2021). As a result, technology has altered how HR managers perform their duties.

The agility that HR management enjoys has also been transformed by technology. Thanks to advancements in technology, HR procedures can now be completed online. Consequently, HR management benefits from agility through the use of e-HRM methods to improve organisational performance (Sutha & Thathsara, 2021). Since HR procedures are executed effectively, e-HRM has helped firms maintain their competitive edge and sustainability (Shamout et al., 2022). Thus, technology affects both the performance of HR professionals and the success of the company as a whole.

Through staff training, communication, and performance tracking, technology also improves HR managers' internal performance. By providing staff with the required technological resources, HR management also improves performance (Prasanna et al., 2019). Technology utilisation fosters innovation and organisational learning, both of which improve business performance

(Bilan et al., 2020). As a result, technology has a variety of effects on how well organizations work.

The majority of organizations are moving towards the implementation of e-HRM, according to the literature currently in publication. Ahmed (2019) asserts that due to the significant levels of automation taking place in a number of industries, e-HRM is essential for HR management. Other academics, however, maintain that in order to fully realise the potential of e-HRM, HR management must continue to value the role that people play in HR practice (Myllymäki, 2021). Therefore, even with a number of technological advancements, human aspects remain important in performance management. Employees' and HR managers' perceptions of the existing e-HRM systems and their usage are not adequately represented in the literature.

The effect of HR management on organizational performance is enhanced by technology. As explained in the literature above, technology improves the effectiveness of HR procedures. Technology can help HR managers be more efficient in tasks like hiring, training, and performance reviews (Vrontis et al., 2021). Efficiency in HR procedures improves the performance of the entire organization (Shamout et al., 2022). Because of this, e-HRM is becoming increasingly prevalent in HR management. The effectiveness of HR procedures improves the performance of the company. Thus, the literature currently in publication implies that technology has an impact on organizational performance. The study will examine whether workers have the authority to make use of the technology to enhance performance.

2.3 Assessing the Need for Staff

"Vacancies that arise from an incumbent's retirement, resignation, promotion, transfer, or termination serve as the catalyst for recruitment and selection." Additionally, openings may arise when new or additional work needs to be done or when there are major changes in procedures, technology, or the situation (Sisson, 2003). Accurately estimating the number of employees the company will need and the knowledge, skills, and competencies these workers will need to meet the organization's needs as outlined in their corporate and business level strategies is one of the many responsibilities of the human resource manager, who works with other members of the organisation, such as operations managers.

Taylor (2010) asserts that it is feasible to project one or two years into the future and make sound predictions about the staffing needs, with the exception of the most unstable situations. This might be the case, but a lot relies on the industry or sector the business operates in. It is far more difficult for businesses operating in highly unpredictable industries, like fast food restaurants, to predict their future demand for human resources than it is for businesses operating in more stable environments, like government offices.

It is critical to any organization's overall success, regardless of the state of the economy, that the right people are hired who have the skills, knowledge, and abilities to work as effectively and efficiently as possible and who also have the potential to help improve the organization's performance and, ultimately, profitability. To guarantee this, a variety of methods can be employed to forecast an organization's future need for human resources as precisely as feasible.

These techniques fall into three basic categories; systematic techniques, managerial judgment and working back from cost (Taylor, 2008)

The systematic technique of assessing the future demand for human resources aims to predict as accurately as possible the future needs of the organization based on the previous and current trends in employment taking into consideration any areas where they have previously experienced difficulties. According to Taylor (2008) the method of predicting future employment demands can subsequently be broken down further into three distinct approaches which are; a. Time series analysis, b. Work study and c. Productivity trend analysis

The time series analysis approach is most commonly and appropriately used in relatively stable business environments such as public service areas. This essentially involves ‘analyzing employment levels over a time (a time series) and using this as a basis for forecasting manpower levels’ (Bramham, 2008). This method is also useful where an organization experiences cyclical fluctuations over certain periods of time.

The ‘work study analysis’ approach is more appropriate where there are no past trends to analysis for instance if the organization is introducing a completely new form of production or even if the company is a new start up and has no previous experience in the market. Where this method is used ‘special studies are undertaken of individual tasks or processes carried out by the organization in order to establish the numbers required to complete them most effectively and efficiently’ (Taylor, 2008). This approach to forecasting future demand is most commonly suited to operations in the manufacturing sector as tasks can be divided into specific roles on the production line. Throughout what is referred to as the development stage work study specialists analyze employees’ performance along with the effectiveness and efficiency of how the tasks are being done and conclude on the best possible approach which will allow them to make predictions for the required staffing levels in the future (Taylor, 2008).

The final approach that can be used under the heading of systematic techniques is productivity trend analysis which is often considered appropriate for the long term forecasting of highly skilled people in areas such as banking or any other service related sector like fast food restaurant. ‘This productivity method of forecasting manpower involves relating one factor with another, either to forecast workload and then use this to forecast manpower or to forecast manpower directly’ (Bramham, 2008). As this forecasting technique relies on the past relationship of production and staffing levels continuing into the future management must be able to use their judgement to identify possible future changes in both the internal and external environment and as a result determine how they will address future staffing needs (Bramham, 2008).

Many firms nowadays rely on the subjective judgments of management to try and estimate their future employment demands. According to Taylor (2008) ‘in instances where the business environment is very volatile and where future staffing patterns may possibly bear little relation to prior experience, there is no choice, if planning is to occur, to adopting educated opinion as a basis for estimates’. According to Stainer (2010), there are a number of advantages which can be derived from this approach to predicting the future human resource requirements of the organization including the fact that ‘it is quick and requires little to no data and also intangible

factors such as changes in fashion, social opinion and taste can be brought into account' (as cited in Taylor, 2010).

One technique which falls under the topic of management judgement is the 'Delphi method'. According to Günaydin (2000) 'the purpose of most Delphi applications is the reliable and creative exploration of ideas or the generation of relevant information for decision making. He further noted that 'the Delphi method is a good communication instrument utilised among a group of experts and consequently aids the formulation of a group judgement'. In terms of human resource planning firms utilising this technique need a number of its managers to provide in writing their own forecasts of the future personnel necessary. The estimations from these projections are then passed back amongst the group of managers who subsequently adjust their calculations depending on the findings of the report. After potentially multiple rounds of estimations and predictions a consensus is achieved by management on the future staffing requirements of the organization.

Although Stainer (2010) noted a number of advantages offered by the management judgment method to projecting human resource demands he also acknowledged the reality that it was not without its draw backs. Stainer feels that 'the intricacy of the process and the number of components at action are often too vast for a single brain or group of brains to cope with' (as reported in Taylor, 2010). Kispal-Vitai and Wood (2009) also stated their uncertainty as to the dependability of management judgement as they 'argue that this kind of approach can amount to little more than a sum of the best guesses' (as reported in Taylor 2010, p.109

The organization's financial foundation serves as the primary foundation for the last method that can be utilised to forecast future personnel demands, working back from costs. If profit and market targets are to be accomplished, the manager should be able to determine how much the company can afford to spend with the assistance of the finance department. The manager must then prepare for a workforce capable of completing the work within a budget, which provides a solid indicator of personnel requirements (Bramham, 2008). One of the primary benefits of this strategy is that managers are not limited by potentially ineffective old techniques because they are working from future projections rather than past experiences.

Employee management includes a wide range of duties that can be broadly divided into several areas:

2.4 Design and Analysis of Job

A job analysis is the next step in the recruitment and selection process once the company has determined that it needs more employees. According to a recent nationwide poll, "more than 30% of CEOs stated that up to half of their employees are a poor fit for their job," according to Pham et al. (2020). To avoid this and guarantee that the right person is hired, it is crucial that individuals in charge of hiring know exactly what position they are hiring for so they can choose the most qualified applicant. Job analysis is the "systematic process of collecting information about the tasks, responsibilities, and contexts of the job," according to Chukwuka & Nwakoby (2018). "A job analysis is an essential foundation for many of the processes that underpin personnel/human resource management practice in organizations, including not only recruitment but also selection, performance appraisal, training and development, and job evaluation,"

according to McMahon & O'Carroll (2009) and Pilbeam & Corbridge (2006), two researchers who have acknowledged that the functions of a job analysis extend beyond the recruitment process.

Since information about the skills, knowledge, and abilities needed to fill the position must be obtained from a variety of sources, the organization is effectively conducting research when creating a job analysis. Depending on the methods employed, the analyst's level of experience, and the intricacy of the work, the line manager or the HR specialist may choose to conduct the job analysis alone or in tandem (Pilbeam and Corbridge, 2006). The information required to create a precise job analysis can also be obtained in a variety of methods, such as through "exit interviews," monitoring people who are actively performing the job, and soliciting feedback from managers, supervisors, and coworkers.

"Ideally, job analysis should comprise the following components: job description, job specification, and person specification," said McMahon & O'Carroll (2009). The job description serves as the foundation for the employment contract since it is "basically a broad statement of the purpose, scope, duties, and responsibilities that are attached to the job" (Gunnigle et al., 2006). A job description will help management determine whether there is a real job vacancy or if there is a gap that occurred from existing employees not performing their duties effectively, in addition to giving them a clear knowledge of the duties the new position will require. Job Title, Department, Location, Reports to Purpose, Main Tasks, Liaison and Main Contacts, Staff Responsibilities, Special Features, Reward, and Conditions are some of the roughly ten components that make up a job description.

The person specification, which is the next part of a job analysis, basically gives the company an overview of the abilities, skills, and knowledge that candidates must have in order to perform the job as effectively and efficiently as feasible. Two authors who are frequently cited in the field of recruitment and selection research are Rodger (2002) and Munro-Fraser (2004). Both authors created frameworks that were fairly similar to help recruiters find the best candidates as precisely and equitably as possible.

The following elements and explanations made up Rodgers' (2002) seven-point plan:

Physical attributes: well-being, looks, demeanour, and speech

Achievements: training, credentials, and experience

General intelligence: the ability to think

Special skills include mechanical aptitude, manual dexterity, and proficiency with language and numbers.

Interests: social, artistic, practical, intellectual, building, and physical

Characteristics: self-reliance, stability, dependability, influence over others, and acceptance

Situation: any unique requirements of the position Similar elements made up Munro-Frasers' (2004) five-fold grading system:

Effects on other people: speech, manners, and physical appearance

Acquired credentials include education, job experience, and vocational training.

Natural aptitudes: rapidity of understanding and learning

Motivation: personal objectives, perseverance, and resolve in pursuing them

Adjustments include emotional stability, stress tolerance, and interpersonal skills (as cited in Beardwell & Holden, 2001).

Despite the fact that these frameworks are frequently cited, some of their components appear to be a little outdated, and some may even have legal ramifications because they relate to candidates' emotional stability" and "make-up," which are listed as grounds for discrimination in the 1999–2006 Equality Act. Organizations' must therefore make sure that, if they choose to use either of these frameworks, they do it in a way that is morally righteous and devoid of discrimination. Organizations' are reminded of the possible legal ramifications of their hiring practices if they unintentionally discriminate against a certain group of people when talking about Rodgers' (2002) and Munro-Frazer's (2004) frameworks. Organizations' that create a precise job analysis, however, have a better chance of creating work and person specifications that are as devoid of prejudice and discrimination as feasible. Consciously or unintentionally, preconceived or deeply ingrained views, prejudices, and assumptions may result in requirements that are less relevant to the job at hand and more focused on satisfying the presumptive demands of clients, coworkers, or the organization's culture. Therefore, organizations are assisting in the prevention of such assumptions by accurately developing a job analysis.

The organization must decide who will be in charge of the recruiting and selection process, when they will be involved and other details before the hiring process can start. When there are several branches spread across a territory, this is very crucial. In this situation, district managers might be tasked with forecasting staffing requirements and completing the various steps of the hiring and selection procedure.

2.5 Recruitment Process

The hiring and selection of employees can be viewed as a process that is well-defined by several consecutive processes, each of which is crucial to finding and hiring qualified applicants (Turner, 2010). The organization must choose its recruitment strategies to draw in the top applicants after determining the need for employees and successfully completing a job analysis. The company must choose whether to hire from within or outside at this point, as well as how to market the open positions and draw in qualified applicants. Organizations should be able to determine through the assessment, job analysis, and design stages whether an individual currently employed by the organization would be able to meet the requirements of the new position or whether an individual from outside the organization would be more suitable.

2.5.1 Internal Recruitment

According to Newell (2005), internal recruitment is a prevalent practice in the private sector, when companies "try to fill vacancies internally before they consider looking for people outside the organization." Internal recruitment can occur for a variety of causes and with a variety of methods. There are four different internal recruitment strategies that an organisation might employ, according to Fuller and Huber (2008). These consist of lateral transfers, internal promotions, job rotation, and rehiring previous staff members. Promotions from within an organisation can accomplish a variety of goals. In addition to meeting the company's staffing needs, they can also address other issues because they are perceived as a kind of reward and incentive for the workers, which may boost their levels of commitment, motivation, and

retention. In his statement that "if promotion remains a motivator for employees, the manager will expect to improve or maintain retention and commitment by a properly managed promotion policy," Bramham (2008) accepts this. According to Chan (2006), "external recruits account for only about 15% to 20% of all appointments to top management positions," therefore promotions are frequently the preferred option when more senior positions within the organisation become available.

Other internal recruitment strategies, such job rotations and lateral transfers, have also worked well in the past since they give staff members a more comprehensive grasp of the many jobs performed in the various departments of the company. The company may also benefit from this since other staff members will be able to cover for any unplanned absences rather than bringing on temporary help when it is not absolutely required.

In order to preserve positive relationships within the company, strong employee morale, and a kind of work incentive, internal recruitment strategies are frequently used. "Internal recruitment provides a higher level of employee satisfaction, so certainly it can be a retention driver," claims Gensing-Pophal (2006). Despite the fact that these criteria encourage businesses to pursue internal recruitment, there is a chance that a position will be filled by a subpar candidate. "It increases the chance of inferior internal contestants being promoted to senior positions," claims Chan (2006). Since there will only be a small number of potentially qualified applicants working within the company as opposed to the potential numbers who could apply if they were to hire from outside, it is critical for the organization to realize that they are significantly reducing the talent pool from which to recruit.

The significant cost effectiveness of internal recruitment procedures is one of the more often mentioned benefits of doing so. Staff notice boards, newsletters, and intranet systems can all be used to promote openings for free. Through the use of this recruitment strategy, companies can save money on advertising, on boarding, and training, among other things. Pham et al. (2020) claim that "hiring an existing employee to fill the vacancy results in savings in the training costs associated with company-specific functions." Since notice boards, word-of-mouth, the workplace intranet, and newsletters can all be used to publicize the new post, the organization can save money right away by avoiding the need to pay for agencies, ads, etc. However, companies should make sure they have the correct kind of employees to cover the position when using this strategy because any future cost savings from hiring could be lost.

The incorrect individual costs you three times their yearly wage, according to a Business Credit story from 2006. As a result, even though the company could have saved money throughout the hiring process, there is a chance that they will have to pay more for missed opportunities and lost clients and business.

Another strategy that businesses have been employing for internal hiring is talent management. As the need for qualified employees grows and recruitment budgets are threatened, talent management systems are making resurgence, claims Hill (2008). Because they should be able to find the right person for the job right away, this enables the company to make effective plans for any future openings.

2.5.2. External Recruitment

Not all abilities can be found internally, and external hiring will always be necessary, claim Pham et al. (2020). The goal of external recruitment is to draw in a wide range of candidates. This can be done through formal methods like advertising in the printed media, outside agencies, education liaison, other media, and professional contacts. Organisations can also use a variety of other strategies, such as using social networking sites like LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, and others, to successfully hire the right candidate. They say that "as the talent pool becomes more diverse and more unpredictable, recruitment becomes trickier." With so many different recruitment strategies now available, companies must make sure they are employing the most efficient ones that will draw in the best applicants, whether that means using more contemporary strategies like online ads or more conventional ones like newspapers and noticeboards.

2.5.3. Informal Recruitment

Using unofficial techniques like word-of-mouth and a speculative application is one popular recruitment strategy. According to Henry and Temtime (2010), "informal recruitment methods are highly associated with smaller organizations and deliver accurate and detailed information about the organization and the job to potential applicants." When informal recruitment takes place, candidates are frequently selected based on recommendations from current staff members or other people who have some sort of connection to the company. Research clearly indicates that informal hiring practices choose more highly qualified candidates than formal hiring practices (Taylor, 2008). One could counter that informal recruitment, like internal hiring, also reduces the number of candidates the company can select from.

An organization's good retention rates are correlated with informal recruitment, according to research in this field. "Candidates who are recruited by word of mouth or approach organizations themselves self-select to a greater degree than those finding out about the job from other sources" (Taylor, 2008) is one of the potential explanations for this. Businesses may view this as a desirable quality in a hiring strategy, but they must also be mindful that by using such tactics, they may be unknowingly discriminating against their employees and limiting their diversity.

2.5.4. Formal Recruitment

Henry and Temtime (2010) state that "the ability of the organization to attract and retain individuals with skills needed to give the organization a competitive edge will depend on the organization's ability to maintain organizational ability and sustain competitive advantage." It may be argued that traditional recruitment methods are preferable in this case since they allow the company to draw in a larger range of applicants, providing them with a far larger talent pool to select from. "A wider pool of applicants is attracted by using traditional recruitment methods" (Henry and Temtime, 2010). When it comes to formal recruitment, organizations can use a variety of strategies.

Employing consultants and employment agencies is one of the many alternatives open to organizations. By choosing to use these third-party agencies, organizations are effectively outsourcing a part of the hiring and selection process; these agencies screen and test applicants before suggesting them for an interview. However, recruitment consultants will also handle the job posting in addition to performing a large portion of the administrative tasks related to hiring.

Because agencies "can provide applicants at short notice," the organization saves a significant amount of time and effort when using this recruitment strategy, both in terms of their involvement in the process and the potential time it takes to find a suitable candidate (McMahon & O'Carroll, 2009). Because agencies and consultants charge about "8-15 per cent of the basic salary," organizations should be sure that the financial costs do not outweigh the possible advantages before deciding to use this recruitment strategy (McMahon & O'Carroll, 2009).

Using the local and national press, including radio, television, and newspapers, is the most conventional and often used method of hiring. Because of their "exclusive and high impact, making it difficult for audiences to ignore – and they immediately research prospects who are not actively seeking a job change," these advertising tools can frequently prove to be very effective (McMahon & O'Carroll, 2009). Because it will attract individuals looking for local jobs and is reasonably priced, using local media is frequently regarded as one of the finest possibilities. It might be more challenging to determine which type of press is best to utilise in big cities, though.

The internet has swiftly become as one of the most popular and economical recruitment channels available. Since networking sites like Facebook, LinkedIn, and Twitter offer a powerful way to advertise new opportunities to a large pool of possible candidates, organisations are become more conscious of the advantages of this recruitment strategy.

2.5.5. Selection Process

The organization's next step is to determine the most suitable and efficient approach to employ in order to choose the best candidate for the position after deciding on the best way to recruit possible candidates. Organizations can pick from a wide range of ways at this point, frequently combining several approaches to increase the likelihood that they will find the greatest fit. A chain of selection is only as strong as its weakest link. A number of difficult choices must be made throughout the selection process, including which person to choose, which techniques to employ, and which information to use. According to Sparow et al. (2004), the selection process is a reciprocal process in which the candidate chooses whether or not to accept a job offer from the organization. According to Ejiofor (2009), selection is the process of selecting candidates for open positions based on the organization's and the job's qualifications.

2.6. The Classic Trio of the Selection Process

According to a recent survey conducted by Melo (2012), 63% of the companies surveyed said they regularly use the traditional three-point process of application forms, interviews, and references, which is the second most popular tool used in the recruitment and selection process by organizations today (Bramham, 2008). Although there are many articles, publications, and studies that support the idea that there are a significant number of alternative recruitment and selection tools available that can predict the suitability of candidates with much greater accuracy, Mark Cook coined the term "classic trio" in 2004 to refer to one of the most popular combinations of recruitment and selection tools used by organizations over the past number of decades.

2.6.1. Application forms and resumes

Approximately 80% of respondents use application forms, per a poll conducted by Taylor (2008). The application form, sometimes known as the curriculum vitae, is the first part of the "classic trio" method to hiring. "This recruitment tool has become so ingrained in the recruitment process that most recruiters take it for granted and candidates completely expect it" (Roberts, 2009).

When a company chooses to adopt the curriculum vitae strategy, they are effectively giving applicants the chance to create their own application, emphasizing the elements they believe are most pertinent to the company and the position they are applying for. According to Taylor (2008), this strategy "gives applicants the freedom to sell themselves in their own way." Some recruiters prefer to use this method because it shows that the candidate can marshal their thoughts and put together a clear piece of communication," according to Roberts (2009). Taylor (2008) contends, however, that applicants are also given the chance to "contaminate" their resume. It happens when "a C.V. is especially well-structured or presented, which may unintentionally cause careless selectors to give preference to applications from otherwise unattractive applicants over those of their more qualified competitors. The application form, on the other hand, is a document with several questions that the applicant must respond to as succinctly as possible because the word count is typically limited. Organizations' that decide to use application forms as a recruitment technique may encounter a number of problems, as several authors have pointed out. The fact that their design's limitations may lead to the exclusion of exceptional candidates is one of the most prominent problems. Another problem with application forms is that companies frequently neglect to modify them to reflect the knowledge, abilities, and skills needed for the position.

To tackle this issue and guarantee the efficacy of application forms as a recruitment tool, Taylor (2008) proposes that "the best solution is to design separate application forms for each vacancy advertised." While this may be the ideal option for organizations in theory, it is sometimes considerably harder to accomplish in practice. "The organization may have a single uniform application or a small number of applications for different kinds of job families, depending on the size of the organization and diversity of roles" (Roberts, 2009).

2.6.2. Interviews

Interviews are "a social encounter between an applicant and a representative of an employer and personalizes the recruitment and selection process," according to Pilbeam and Corbridge (2006). An interview can be organized, focusing on a predetermined set of well-defined criteria, or unstructured, involving a free-flowing conversation (Roberts, 2009). The possibility of evaluating each applicant according to different standards is one of the primary concerns that have been brought to light in relation to unstructured interviews. According to Taylor (2008) "the traditional interviewer gathers information in a relatively unsystematic manner and may reach judgments about candidates on a number of different grounds" because candidates may be asked a variety of questions. This makes it more challenging to thoroughly evaluate possible applicants, and the ideal fit can be missed. Organizations' that use interviews extensively as a recruitment strategy must make sure the person conducting the interview is as objective as possible because bias is a big issue with this method. "Interviewers tend to make up their minds

within the first few minutes of the interview and the remainder of the time is spent confirming these first impressions," claim Pilbeam and Corbridge (2006).

Although there have been many critiques of the interview's efficacy over the years, managers from all sectors and industries continue to use it as one of the most common recruitment methods, according to the results of the Sission (2003) survey. Potential candidates anticipate going through it as part of the application process, which is another recruitment strategy. Although the precise cause of this recruitment technique's continued popularity has not been determined, experts, scholars, and writers have all offered theories as to why it is still so widely used despite the more sophisticated and successful approaches that are currently accessible.

The fact that this recruitment tool is among the most economical methods an organisation can employ to evaluate suitable applicants is one of the primary justifications offered by the professionals for its continued use. One explanation, according to Taylor (2010), is the notion that basic one-on-one interviews are more effective than ineffectual as predictive methods because of their comparatively low cost.

According to Herriot (2002), the fact that the interview enables a face-to-face interaction between the interviewer and the candidate is another factor contributing to its ongoing appeal. The interviewer "thinks that only by these means can they discover whether the applicant is likely to fit in to the organization – whether others will like him or her and will work well together," according to Herriot.

Herriot (2002) proposes two further potential explanations for the persistence of the popularity of interviews: negotiating and mutual review (Taylor, 2008). Organisations may believe that the interview provides a chance for candidates to ask questions to learn more about the position, according to Herriot. Additionally, it could give the applicant a general understanding of the organization's culture, values, and ideas. This could also assist the candidate in determining whether they truly desire the position.

Last but not least, it is thought that interviews might be crucial in presenting the company as a top employer. Taylor (2008) asserts that "there is every benefit to sending candidates away believing that they would like the job if it were offered to them, determined to seek other positions within the organization if other opportunities present themselves, and willing to speak well of the organization because of the efficiency, effectiveness, fairness, and courtesy displayed towards them."

2.6.3. Reference Letter

The use of references has grown more problematic over the past ten years for all parties involved; people are having trouble getting references from past employers, employers are becoming less willing to provide them, and potential employers are having trouble finding objective, truthful statements about possible hires. Since the idea now has legal ramifications, the legitimacy of references as sufficient hiring tools has been under intense scrutiny, particularly in recent years. "The reference letter has low validity as a predictor of job performance and has been found to say more about its author than about its subject," claims Taylor (2010).

According to an essay by Arkin (2005), organisations may experience issues whether they are asking for or giving the reference. The author does, however, add that although handling

references can be challenging for everyone involved, it can also be highly advantageous for the company attempting to determine whether applicants are qualified for the role.

The risk of giving a simple reference has grown dramatically over the past few years as employers have become more conscious of the dangers they face if they give a reference that presents the candidate in a negative light or if they decide not to hire someone based on a reference about the candidate. Therefore, some will merely confirm dates of employment, pay, and position to potential employers due to the growing possibility of "discrimination and slander suits from former employees" (HR People, 2009).

According to Arkin (2005), it is more usual for former employers to provide a more detailed explanation of an employee's performance verbally rather than in writing if they are ready to do so. According to an article by Arkins (2005), "people are willing to say things on the phone that they wouldn't write down in today's litigious society." On the phone, you can make references to topics that are not possible on paper. The validity of this recruitment technique is always being examined due to the hazards involved in both providing references and using them as the basis for decisions. But according to the (Mello, 2012) poll, this strategy is still among the most widely used ones for hiring today, along with the other two elements of the "classic trio."

2.6.4. Psychometric testing

The increasing emphasis on psychometric testing as a recruitment tool is one of the most talked-about trends in recruitment and selection today. In order to assess individual differences, such as those in personality, aptitude, ability, accomplishment, or intellect, psychometric tests are those that can be administered and scored in a systematic manner (Pilbeam & Corbridge, 2006).

2.6.5. Work Simulation/Samples

Ployhart (2006) states that "work samples give candidates a series of exercises or tasks that are almost exactly the same as those done on the job." This enables the assessors to evaluate the candidates based on a factor that is pertinent to the job for which they are applying. Work samples are seen to be one of the most effective means of achieving both validity and diversity at the same time (Ployhart, 2006).

When it comes to recruitment and selection, tray exercises can be utilised. The process involves giving each candidate a variety of materials to go through and clearly outline the steps they would take to address each issue.

2.6.6. Biographical Data

This method of selection has been around for a while, but only recently has it caught the interest of several scholars in the field of recruiting and selection. Only a small percentage of organizations utilize this strategy. In essence, this method of hiring "involves using detailed information concerning an applicants' past to make deductions about his or her likely performance in the future," however it can take many different forms (Taylo, 2008). Applications, resumes, interviews, and other sources can provide this information.

Pilbeam and Corbridge (2006) state that "the use of bio data is predicted on two beliefs: first, that prior experiences and circumstances shape distinctive behaviour patterns, and therefore abilities; and second, that one can predict future behaviour and consequent job performance by accessing

the individual's experiences and circumstances." Because the design, development, and usage of a systematic bio data system are specific to each organization and job, organizations that decide to utilise this method of selection must first make sure that they have conducted an accurate job analysis. According to a recent study by Harvey-Cook & Taffler (2000), "the scored bio data approach has been criticized for (a) lack of stability, (b) apparently mystifying relationships between independent and dependent variables, (c) organizational-specificity, and (d) susceptibility to faking." They also acknowledged that over time, a number of criticisms have surfaced regarding bio data as a selection tool.

2.6.7. Centres for Assessment

"The assessment centre is a diagnostic tool in which several judges examine applicants' performance in job-related simulations," according to Dayan et al. (2008). Testing, interviews, and job simulations are some of the methods used to evaluate applicants when assessment centres are selected as the selection tool. The following traits define assessment centres, which are the best illustration of a multi-evaluation procedure:

1. The rigorous definition of the assessment criteria is typically accomplished through role analysis.
2. The evaluation techniques are closely aligned with these standards.
3. For every criterion area, many assessors and assessment methods are used.

1. Candidates usually undergo the evaluation procedure in groups, and each assessment program is followed by a comprehensive integration session (Rush, 2009).

Assessment centres have received accolades for their precision and efficiency over the years. They are regarded as an efficient selection tool for hiring managers and other higher level employees since they are helpful in "extracting behaviours relating to interpersonal relationships, leadership, influencing ability, sociability, competitiveness, self-motivation, tolerance, persuasiveness, problem analysis, and decisiveness" (Pilbeam & Corbridge, 2006). Thornton (2008) states that "this method has demonstrated high validity and effectiveness in predicting managerial success according to varying criteria and is commonly utilised for the selection and promotion of higher level managerial positions" (as stated in Dayan et al., 2008). Nevertheless, despite being one of the most successful strategies, this strategy has two significant disadvantages for organisations: it is expensive and time-consuming. It would be unwise for organisations to use them when hiring lower level employees, like cleaning workers, because of these issues.

2.6.8. Evaluating the Process

Every organization has a very different and complex process for designing and developing its recruitment and selection procedures. It is crucial that the organization assess the process in a way that will reveal any shortcomings and correct them appropriately in order to make sure that it has put in place an efficient procedure that is meeting the needs of the company as effectively and efficiently as possible. From the job analysis and design to the selection techniques employed, it is critical that every step of the hiring process be assessed.

Performance management systems are one tool that may be used to evaluate how well the hiring process is working. This can be accomplished by contrasting the performance of the employees with the job requirements provided in the job description. It is a sign that the hiring and selection

process did not find the right applicant for the position if the employee does not meet the expectations during the probationary term.

2.7. Development and Training

"Training is the act of increasing the knowledge and skills of an employee for doing a particular job," according to Dyer (2009). Training is any procedure that improves a person's attitudes, abilities, and skills to perform a given job. The practice of methodically fostering knowledge in people with the aim of enhancing performance is known as training. According to Polyant (2006), employee relations procedures, training and development procedures, and issues with efficiency and flexibility all have an impact on organizational productivity.

A workforce that is multi skilled, flexible, and has extensive conceptual knowledge of the industrial system can be produced with proper training (Huselid, 2005). Higher productivity and happier employees are the results of a close relationship between training and employee commitment. According to Bowen & Ostroff's (2004) investigation on the relationship between training and organizational commitment, perceived access to training had the strongest associations with organizational commitment. The findings demonstrated that workers were more devoted to their company because they saw training as an indication of their employer's support. Enhancing human capital through ongoing training can boost each worker's productivity by raising their skill level or by boosting their morale and job satisfaction (Delery & Doty, 2006).

According to Schuler and Jackson (2009), the main shortcomings of many training systems in developing countries include the absence of clear training policies, the inadequate alignment of training with broader development objectives, and the failure to connect training design to future demands. Schuler and Jackson (2009) proposed the Strategic Training System to manage training's constraints.

2.8. Performance Appraisal

Performance appraisal is the process of assessing how well employees perform their jobs in relation to a set of standards and then informing those employees of that information (Blau, 2004). Baron (2010) states that "Performance appraisal is the systematic, periodic, and impartial rating of an employee's excellence in matters pertaining to his present job and his potential for a better job." A thorough and widely used evaluation system can help managers make decisions about each employee and give employees insightful feedback (Hitt et al., 2001).

A systematic performance management method is not commonly used in professional conversations, as Shrinivas Kandula (2006) noted in his work "Integrated Performance Management Model: A Tool for Creating High Performance Culture." According to Colbert (2004), managers are inherently opposed to methodical planning and staff performance monitoring. He goes on to say that bad performance management procedures are influenced by the subjective style of top management as well as a lack of knowledge when it comes to determining key result areas.

Performance management is frequently thought of as only an enhanced variant of the performance appraisal system. In Nigeria, only a very small number of companies use performance management as a full-fledged system. These companies are primarily found in the new economy, with software, IT-enabled services, financial services, pharmaceuticals, and green field manufacturing setups, and they are rarely found in the old economy. Nonetheless, a rising

number of organisations in the commercial and public sectors—both corporate and non-corporate—are realising how important it is to implement a scientific performance management system that can foster a high-performance culture.

2.9. Employee Productivity

The term "employee productivity" describes how well a worker uses their time, abilities, and resources to complete tasks and support corporate objectives. You can use the brief, well-organized notes below for work-related presentations, teaching, or research. The quantity and caliber of work an employee completes in a specific length of time is measured by employee productivity, which is frequently contrasted with inputs like time, effort, or cost. While low productivity can raise expenses and turnover, high productivity boosts profitability, customer happiness, and operational effectiveness.

Basic strategies to increase output:

1. To help employees know what to aim for, set SMART goals (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time-bound).
2. Promote independence and adaptability, such as remote work or flexible scheduling, while emphasizing results rather than hours worked.
3. Give regular feedback and acknowledgment, including commendation and prizes for accomplishments.
4. Teach supervisors to do brief, planned progress check-ins and to coach rather than micromanage.
5. Reduce distractions (such as pointless meetings and cluttering tools) and encourage time-management techniques like task batching and prioritization.

Measuring worker productivity

typical metrics consist of:

1. Production per hour (e.g., tickets handled, units generated).
2. Quality metrics (client satisfaction ratings, mistake rates).
3. Goal completion rate in relation to predetermined KPIs or targets.

3.0 Methodology

This study used a cross-sectional survey research design and collected primary data from fast food establishments in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria, which make up the study population. The population and sample elements will only focus on the management team of the selected fast food restaurant in Asaba, Delta State, which employs 133 people in total. The justification for choosing only management staff is that they are with the responsibility of deploying employee management strategies for optimum productivity in Nigeria as well as in charge of managing all HRM practices, and activities within the organization.

4. Result

Analysis of Research Questions

Department “A”: Personnel Data of Respondents

Table 1: Age Distribution of Respondents

Age	No. Of Respondents	Percentage (%)
18-28yrs	35	32.41
28-38yrs	42	38.9
38-48yrs	23	21.3
48-58yrs	8	7.40
Total	108	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

According to the age distribution table in this case, 35 respondents, or 32.41%, were between the ages of 18 and 28; 42 respondents, or 38.9%, were between the ages of 28 and 38; 23 respondents, or 21.3%, were between the ages of 38 and 48; and 8 respondents, or 7.40%, were between the ages of 49 and older. The information in the age distribution table has been statistically presented and analyzed.

Table 2: Academic qualification of respondents

Academic Qualification	No of Respondents	Percentage%
SSCE	28	25.93
NCE/OND	30	27.8
HND/B.SC	35	32.41
MSC	15	13.9
PhD	-	-
Total	108	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

According to the data analysis demonstration, it is truthful to say that 28 respondents, or 25.93% of the sample, held an SSCE certificate, 30 respondents, or 27.8%, were drawn from the NCE/OND, 35 respondents, or 32.41%, and 15 respondents, or 13.9%, held an MSc certificate, while no respondents or percentages were found for the PhD. The study's academic qualification distribution table's statistical results are displayed in the table.

4.1. Criteria, Respondents, and Group Returns

According to table I above, 108 of the 133 copies of the surveys that were distributed—or 81%—were returned.

Summary of responses using five point Likert’s scale

S/N	Questionnaire	SA	A	U	D	SD
1	Modern employee management strategies used in your firm are directly connected with your organizational productivity.	48	45	5	10	0
2	Modern employee management strategies are improving the productivity of your modern businesses	50	43	5	8	4
3	Modern employee management strategies of your modern organization have helped to retain staff.	40	43	3	17	5
4	Modern employee Management strategies of your modern organization is helping your business to survive.	39	49	5	13	2

5	The recruitment process of your modern organization is helping your business to retain her staff and survive the business	57	40	4	7	0
6	Selection process of your modern business hire only the best talents to your organization	35	52	5	19	0
7	Training and development of your modern organization has led to staff motivation	45	39	4	16	4
8	Training and development of your modern business has improved employee performance	46	51	0	10	19
9	Training and development of staff of your organization has led to the retention of your best talents	41	58	0	9	2
10	Your modern organization engages is periodic staff training and development	49	54	31	1	1
11	Adequate Human resource planning and implementation has led to the survival of your modern business	38	50	2	6	2
12	Human resource management practices of your modern organization is positively connected to the survival of your business	35	63	0	7	3

Field Survey 2026

4.2 Hypothesis Testing

Hi: Modern Employee Management Strategies are significantly and directly connected to Optimum Organizational Productivity.

One-Sample Test						
Questions	Test Value =0					
	T	Df	Sig (Two tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
5	1.8901901	4	.130	21.60000	-9.9417	-53.1417
6	2.308	4	.082	22.20000	-12.3772	55.5772
7	1.931	4	.126	17.80000	-7.7885	43.3885
8	1.904	4	.130	21.40000	-9.8100	52.6100

4. DISCUSSION

The five questions in the one sample t-test table above yield a good result. The table t-value is 1.812, whereas the computed t-value is 8.044. This indicates that the computed t-value (8.044>1.812) is higher than the table t-value. As a result, we reject the null hypothesis and support the alternative hypothesis, which proved that Modern Employee Management Strategies are significantly and directly connected to Optimum Organizational Productivity.

The hypothesis demonstrated that Modern Employee Management Strategies are significantly and directly connected to Optimum Organizational Productivity. This finding is consistent with

the finding of Chukwuka & Nwakoby (2018). It also showed a strong and favourable or significant connection between recruitment and selection procedures and the survival of contemporary enterprises as well as organizational performance. This indicates that hiring and selecting the greatest talent is one way that human resource management methods may help modern firms perform better and survive. They can also help employees cultivate a positive work attitude.

The study discovered a strong positive relationship between organizational performance, human resource planning, and the survival of contemporary firms. Similarly, the study concludes that a human-centric HRM approach of HRM planning is necessary in the modern workplace to guarantee complete employee engagement and the best talent retention in modern business. This is crucial since it increases the organization's overall productivity, survivability, and sustainability. As a result, companies should make sure that their HR practices are human-centered. The study also demonstrated a strong and positive correlation between the success of contemporary companies and the efficiency of their hiring and selecting procedures.

This implies that human resource management's recruitment and selection processes can help employees cultivate a good work attitude and enhance the performance and survival of modern firms by attracting and choosing the best applicants. The empirical study found a substantial correlation between organizational success, training and development, and the survival of contemporary businesses. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Khan, & Abdullah, (2019). These findings show that better employee performance and the survival of contemporary businesses are closely related to the training and development function of human resource management. The study's conclusions indicate that human resource management techniques, such as employee training and development, hiring and selection procedures, and human resource planning, have the potential to significantly change the workplace by retaining top talent and boosting employee engagement and productivity.

5. Conclusion

The study's conclusions show that modern employee management strategies and organizational productivity are significantly and positively correlated. This is crucial since it increases the organization's overall productivity, survivability, and sustainability. As a result, companies should make sure that their HR practices are human-centered. The study also demonstrated a strong and favorable relationship between the effectiveness of hiring and selecting procedures and the survival of contemporary enterprises. This implies that human resource management's recruitment and selection processes can help employees cultivate a good work attitude and enhance the performance and survival of modern firms by attracting and choosing the best applicants. The empirical study found a substantial correlation between organizational success, training and development, and the survival of contemporary businesses. The study concludes that a human-centric HRM approach and modern employee management strategies are necessary in the modern workplace to guarantee full employee engagement and the best talent retention in modern business as well as optimum organizational productivity

5.1. Recommendation

Based on the above empirical findings, therefore this study recommends that modern organizations combine the above-mentioned comprehensive and human-centric HRM practices and employee management strategies with AI workplace automation, which shortens turnaround times and increases organizational productivity and effectiveness. The introduction of AI should be human-centered and not aimed at replacing human labour.

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